

COMPARATIVE GLOBAL AID POLITICS AND ASSISTANCE OF TRADITIONAL DONORS AND NEO-DONORS

Muzammil Ahad Dar

Assistant Professor Political Science
Kumarguru College of Liberal Arts and Science
dr.ahad1986@gmail.com

Shanawaz Qadri

Assistant Professor Political Science
University of Kashmir

Abstract

The world is facing sad paradox of deprivation when the global annual arms expenditure is \$US 1800 billion which is ten times more than the expenditure required for addressing global hunger. A week's global arms expenditure is enough to send every single child to school in this world. Around 262 million children are out of school globally according to 2017 assessment of UNESCO. Million Child died due to malnutrition a year as per WHO. It is assessed that US\$ 3.2 billion are essentially required to save global child hunger. Around US\$ 9000 billion aid and an average of US\$ 152.3 billion Official Development Assistance is doled out to 173 countries in six decades, however, the child hunger deaths still prevailing globally. Foreign aid assistance has begun with Marshal plan and WARSAW pact. It was an institutionalized program to serve the national interests of donors. However present day aid assistance is more organized and diversified. Spanning from humanitarian assistance to official Development assistance- the club of donors is also expanding. However, the unfortunate global problems of sanitation, hunger, child mortality and extreme deprivation still persist globally. It is thus aim of this research to understand the instrument, politics and objective of foreign aid assistance. What are mechanism and purposes of aid, how is it delivered and governed, what does it achieve and what it is required to attain the objective of aid assistance.

Keywords:

1. Introduction

During the natural calamities like flood, earth quake or any such disaster that confronts a country, lot of international sympathy in terms of money material and kind flows in. They are all part of International Foreign assistance and aid can be in the form of money, material and manpower too or in many other forms. Interestingly, foreign assistance and international aid can be donated or as per Organization Economic cooperation and Development (OECD) definition, it can be loaned also. However, generally such loans are often loans and they are extended by foreign governments, organizations and individuals in rich countries to help people in affected areas.

The example of Kerala flood for that matter 2018 August, during this massive flood lot of international help was offered to be given. In the case of Indonesian earth quake in 2015 also international help went in. In the case of Haiti- Hurricane 'Mathew' or in the case of developed countries like USA Hurricane Harvey in Texas, international help also came in. These are all cases or examples of Humanitarian Assistance.

Foreign assistance is also referred as International Aid, Economic Aid or Development Aid. Apart from the Humanitarian assistance it can also be extended to war ravaged countries like Afghanistan or many of the sub Saharan countries. Americans reached with humanitarian assistance in Afghanistan. The American Aid agency USAID is conducting training programme in an agrarian field in Mozambique. The lot of international aid comes in for health sanitation and major such programmes covering HIV/AIDS programmes, Malaria eradication and so on.

Interestingly at globally where are the aid or what you call development assistance is being largely located, we see that Africa has been the largest recipient of it. In addition to Africa there have been number of cases in South Asia and many other parts of the world where aid is been extended. Largely therefore, humanitarian assistance or Official Development Assistance (ODA's), they cover funding for variety of purposes like humanitarian assistance, like disaster management or it can be for education, it can be for food, it can be for water, it can be for capacity building training programmes and many such purposes covering multiple sectors. International foreign assistance is extended

for variety of purposes. However, what captures the larger purpose of such donations is humanitarian aid followed by growing aid for refugee costs. Other net ODA donations are for many bilateral or multilateral sectoral assistance programs including capacity building etc. Additionally multiple funding institutions are now more and more finding health sector challenges like malaria eradication, HIV/AIDS programmes, sanitation as well as education, joint research for capacity building in target countries and locations.

This paper examines the instrument of foreign aid, the politics, objective and usefulness of foreign aid, and mechanism and purpose through which aid is delivered and governed and finally what it has achieved and what needs to be done to achieve the objective of foreign aid.

Having been defined in multiple ways, foreign aid standard working definition today comes from the Development Assistance Committee (DAC) of Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) which has been measuring resource flows to developing countries since 1961. The DAC first defined ODA in 1969, and refined the definition in 1972 (OECD, 2018). OECD uses ODA as the key measure practically for all aid targets and assessments of aid performance and DAC has listed recipient countries and institutions for suitable audit of aid performance. As per DAC, ODAs are “those flows to countries and territories on the DAC list of Recipients and to multilateral institutions which are:

- (i) Provided by ‘official agencies’, including state and local governments, or by their executive agencies; and
- (ii) Each transaction of which: a) is administered with the promotion of the economic development and welfare of developing countries as its main objective; and b) is concessional in character and conveys a grant element of at least 25% (calculated at a rate of discount of 10%)” (OECD, 2018).

Foreign Assistance Sectoral Distribution

International foreign assistance is extended for variety of purposes. However, what captures the larger purpose of such donations is humanitarian aid followed by a growing aid for refugee costs (see Fig.1). Other net ODA donations are for many bilateral/multilateral sectoral assistance programmes including capacity building etc. Additionally multiple funding institutions are now more and more funding health sector challenges like malaria irradiation, HIV/AIDS programmes, sanitation as well as education, joint research for capacity building in target countries and locations.

Evolving Foreign Aid Governance

Paris Declaration 2005 was a globally critical mile stone in foreign aid governance. Foreign aid performance assessment is now a priority for aid reallocations. Foreign aid governance in the last over six decades can be largely classified into four or five phases. As shown in the Fig.2. In 1960s & 1970s, donor countries extended wholesome aid mainly for nation building, promoting production capacity and basic human needs. In the second phase in 1980s donor countries largely shifted foreign aid focus to issues of macroeconomic stabilization, structural adjustment and debt reduction of recipient countries. In the third phase in 1990s, in the background of Soviet Union collapse and global economic

liberalisation, donors more focussed on political and economic transition in Eastern Europe and the former Soviet Union.

Foreign aid governance in last six decades	
1960-1970	Aid for nation building, production capacity and basic human needs
1980s	Donors focused on macroeconomic stabilization, structural adjustment and debt reduction
1990s	Soviet Union collapsed and Economic Liberalisation, donors more focused on political and economic transition in East Europe & former Soviet Union
2000 onward	UNOs MDG & first time donor countries shifted focus to poverty reduction, social infrastructure, including health education sanitization & importantly on Effective Aid Governance and performance based aid allocation

By the beginning of 21st century, it was largely rather known that foreign aid seriously suffers from delivery and target meeting challenges. Through a series of aid effectiveness initiatives since 2002 like the „International Conference on Financing for Development“ in Monterrey, Mexico, popularly known as Monterrey Consensus; followed by 2003 „High Level Forum on Harmonization in Rome“ and finally the „Paris Declaration 2005“ and „Accra Agenda for Action 2008“, more than 100 developing and developed countries devised a broader aid effectiveness methodology to be adhered by all by 2010 (Brown, 2016). While Paris Declaration formulated five central pillars like Programme Ownership by recipient countries, Target Alignment, Harmonization, Managing for Results and donor-recipient Mutual Accountability; Accra Agenda affirmed „responsibility commitment“ towards target oriented and transparent foreign aid governance.

Global Institutional Donors

Apart from Govt. – to – Govt. foreign assistance, International Institutions have been a good vehicle for foreign aid disbursement.

During 1960-2016, such institutions have doled out over US \$ 904 billion which is nearly 10% of the total global disbursement. Prominent institutional donors like IDA, EDF, EC and number UN agencies disburse more than 75% of the total such institutional disbursements. Other private institutions like Melinda & Bill Gates Foundation, Macarthur Foundation et al also are donor agencies of repute.

Foreign Aid Donors: Who are they?

Foreign Aid donor countries can be classified into three broad categories. First, the early European and North American donors along with Australia, New Zealand and Japan who are discussed below. Second category is the International Institutional Donors who of late play a big financial assistance role. Third category is the several developing countries who continue to receive aid but have emerged as Neo-Donors in the last over three decades.

Conventional Donors:

First, the early donors or conventional donor countries (Fig.4.) who were the pioneers of foreign aid in the post 2 World War times who were soon joined with Australia, New Zealand and Japan and later South Korea. OECD data lists twenty-nine top donor countries of the world since 1950. These have been the largest donors of the world in the last around 70 years.

The United States followed by Japan, Germany, France and Britain have cumulatively provided over US\$ 2000 billion- largest foreign aid during 1950-2017. The United States is the single largest donor today with annual average of around US\$ 35 billion assistance.

On the other hand, nearly 85% of the traditional donor countries are from Europe (Fig.5), with 57% aid share and outnumbering donor countries from other regions.

Foreign Assistance: Neo Donors

In the last over three decades, China, Taiwan, Arab Countries, India, Brazil, Turkey and even Venezuela and many more countries while still receiving foreign aid, have emerged as neo- foreign aid donors too. We analyze here the case of China, Arab Countries and India as Neo-Donors case analysis.

Fig.5. Global Distribution of Donor Countries 1950-2017

Source: <http://www.oecd.org/dac/financing-sustainable-development/>

China's Foreign Assistance Programme:

China has emerged as a big donor country in this century. While Chinese foreign assistance out flows remains less transparent, most cited Chinese assistance data is from AidData- a research lab at Virginia-based College of William & Mary.

Source: AidData

As per AidData, China's official foreign assistance, including foreign aid, concessional and non-concessional state financing, between 2000 - 2014 stand at US\$ 354 billion to around 140 countries while United States committed US\$ 394.6 billion clearly elevating China to the big donor club.

While Africa and Asia are China's top foreign aid recipients, Central and South American and Caribbean countries are China's primary aid locations too. However, China's foreign assistance in Central America, Caribbean and South Pacific Islands like Solomon Island, Vanuatu, Papua New Guinea, Kiribati, Tuvalu and Nauru remain significant as Chinese use large donations to influence these Island nations to decline their political concessions to Taiwan (Squires, 2006).

Beginning with 20 million Swiss Franc aid to Egypt during 1956 Suez Crisis, Chinese foreign assistance has grown manifold today. China watchers are critical that China uses foreign aid predatorily for huge infrastructure projects and variety of monopoly trade concessions driving recipients into debt trap (Chandran, 2017).

Best case example is Sri Lankan Hambantota Port deal and China-Pakistan CPEC or China's alleged land grab in Djibouti. Soon after receiving South-China Sea/ Nine Dashes negative Hague verdict in July 2016, China quickly waived off all outstanding loans of Cambodia to preempt ASEAN countries negative joint statement and offered Chinese aid to Philippines, whose new President, Rodrigo Duterte, made overtures to Beijing (Singh, 2017). China's top ten aid recipients are mostly challenged countries whose vulnerability seems to have been traded.

The Less Discussed Arab Donors:

Following UAE's US\$ 5.89 billion in foreign aid in 2013, UAE was crowned as the world's top humanitarian donor that year (Dali-Balta, 2015). In September 2014, UN Secretary General Ban Ki-Moon specially honored Kuwait for its role as a „humanitarian leader“ in the Arab world and beyond (Minor, 2014). Arab countries foreign assistance programme is the story of biggest donors worldwide today. In 2017, UAE alone doled out US\$ 4 billion making UAE as the world's largest donor of official development aid relative to its national income (Abdulmalik, 2018). In the last over 10 years, Saudi Arabia alone has extended nearly \$33 billion in global aid (Abdulmalik, 2018). As per OECD data, Saudi Arab has undoubtedly emerged as the biggest donor from the Arab world extending 67% of the regional assistance followed by Kuwait 16%, UAE 10% and others 7%.

Source:
<http://siteresources.worldbank.org/INTMENA/Resources/ADAPub82410web.p>

Kuwait established Kuwait Fund for Arab Economic Development in 1961. A decade later in 1971, the UAE, following Kuwait, founded the Abu Dhabi Fund for Arab Economic Development now called Abu Dhabi Fund (Neumayer, 2002). Now Arab ODA dominated largely by Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, UAE, Oman and Qatar is much more organized providing assistance to poor countries in sub-Saharan Africa such as Mali, Mauritania, Senegal, Somalia, and Sudan; and in Asia such as Cambodia, Bangladesh, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, Tajikistan, and Vietnam.

Recipient to Donor: India's Long Journey

Kerala Flood Assistance Case:

August 2018 Kerala flood generated huge global concern and UAE offered to donate Rs. 700 Cr. and Govt. of Thailand also proposed support. In both the cases, Govt. of India politely declined the financial aid (Express Web Desk, 2018). Also in 2013, India refused US Secretary of State John Kerry's US\$150,000 American aid for Uttarakhand flood victims while opting for multilateral bodies like World Bank or Asian Development Bank loans to manage the crisis (Kasturi, 2013).

Indian Assistance to USA:

On the other hand, on 13 September 2005, an Indian army aircraft landed on a United States Air Force base in Little Rock, Arkansas with 25 tons of relief supplies for the hurricane Katrina victims of New Orleans. At around the same time, the World Food Program (WFP), a major net provider of food assistance in India until the early 2000s, recognized India as its 15th largest donor (Murthy, March 2011).

India's World Food Aid:

In 2009, Nicole Menage, procurement head, WFP HQ in Rome, praised India for selling rice well below market price to WFP which fed hungry people in 22 countries, including Liberia and Sierra Leone in West Africa, Haiti in the Caribbean, and Laos and East Timor in Asia and enabled WFP save US\$ 43million (Skullerud, 2009).

Cyclone Aid to Pakistan: India's Curious Case:

In 2010 cyclone that ravaged nearly a fifth of Pakistan and UNO called for over US\$460 million aid relief fund, India quickly offered US\$5 million in assistance. Given the bilateral hostility, Pakistan quickly refused to receive Indian aid. As the case may happen, finally India increased the aid amount to US\$25 million and placed the aid to United Nations and Pakistan received the Indian aid not directly from India but from UNO (Esselborn, 2010). This made India the 9th biggest donor (larger than China's) to Pakistan (Josua, 2010).

Foreign Aid: India's Soft Power Diplomacy

Apart from force donations to Pakistan and humanitarian assistance to developed countries like USA and Japan, India has steadily projected herself as a donor country ready to shoulder international responsibility and leadership.

During 2009-10, India provided US\$ 383.01 million in foreign aid and loans to South Asian countries with the exception of Pakistan (Bhogal, 2016).

In 2015-16, India's foreign assistance amount expanded to US\$ 1.149 billion. Curiously, in the same year, while India received a total foreign aid of US\$ 0.35 billion, India disbursed US \$1.2 billion as aid to Bhutan-74.6%; Afghanistan- 9.1%; Sri Lanka-6.6%; Nepal-4% and 2.8% each to Bangladesh and Maldives. India's aid allocation pattern remaining similar over the last decade, Bhutan has been India's favorite aid destination in South Asia (Upadhyay, 2018). In terms of India's quantitative aid receipt and disbursement, in 2015-16, India received US \$ 21.4477 billion in aid and donated as much as US \$ 77.1965 billion- more than three times than what India received (Mitra, 2018).

India's aid diplomacy in South Asian neighbourhood goes back to 1950s, Regional Soft Power Diplomacy" under the Colombo Plan (Lowe, 2010). Initiated as a regional multilateral cooperation module against communist rise, Colombo Plan provided a platform to India's aid support in the region. Though Indian aid remained modest, India continued to be the fifth largest donor and largest developing country donor in the neighbourhood beginning with assistance to Nepal during Royal Nepal coup in early 1950s (Dut, 1980).

Indian aid programme has evolved now. India now officially refuses to accept aid other than ODAs or private / government aid for health sector etc. but doles out disaster relief aid where ever needed. On the other hand India has clearly emerged as donor country officially and philosophically extending humanitarian and disaster relief grants and carefully crafting Indian aid programme to paddle India's soft diplomacy for regional as well as global strategic purposes.

Foreign Aid Performance: Field Reports

Linda Polmann- a freelance journalist working for two Dutch news papers, in her TEDx Talks (Polmann, 2011) based on her ground reporting, analyses what's wrong in foreign aid delivery on ground. Citing UN report, Linda points out that there are over seventy donor countries who host foreign aid and a competing number of over thirty-seven thousand foreign aid agencies working in worst hit war ridden zones like Sierra Leone, Congo, Ivory Coast, Liberia, Sudan, Ethiopia, Afghanistan and Haiti- the locations Linda calls them as darling aid destinations for donor countries/organizations. Based on her field reporting, Linda finally concludes that the foreign aid is an industry. More than the goal of delivering positive development interventions to the worst affected people, Linda confesses, these donor industries, with industrial zeal, literally distribute hundreds of billions of dollar to all the perpetrators of war crime, middle men and brokers and very little reach to the deprived target constituency. Further, Linda explains, since hundreds of billions of dollar are rolled out every year, more and more donor agencies compete increasingly with each other to stake claim of the pie. Most such donors, without any strategic planning, doll out higher and higher money to project their donor agency's good work so that they are again eligible for higher grants.

Several other aid workers, academics and field investigators do corroborate to similar findings. Dr. Maliha Chishti- former Director, Hague Appeal for Peace at the United Nations and a researcher specializing in war and post-conflict peace building, shares her similar findings in Afghanistan. Maliha goes further to say that the whole foreign aid industry works on profit basis too with every dollar being rolled out, nearly US\$7- US\$10 comes back to the donor countries (Chishti, 2016).

Similar voices of concern citing Dutch aid agency work on an Indian village (Parajuli, 2017); by Abhishek Parajuli and Masako Yonekawa's field narrative of 2004 tsunami ravaged Indonesia; 1990s war ravaged Congo where more than 6 million people died and people flee even today and all the aid were siphoned off by armed rebels to buy more weapons and finally Fukushima 2011 nuclear disaster in Japan (Yonekawa, 2012) tell similar stories to the extent of saying that aid hurts more than benefits.

Contrary to these material aid distribution and the reports of their agonizing counter productiveness, there are positive experiences too in the field of eradication of disease through foreign aid programmes. Joe Cerrell's experience in Ghana in eradicating Guinea worms through Bill Gates aid programme (Cerrell, 2013). Also David Walton's experience in Haiti dealing with child mortality and other disease during Haitian earth quake where billions of dollars were donated but apparently only 0.09% reached the target needy group. At the end however, Walton shares the joy of hospital building citing the need for infrastructure and capacity building which could reverse the vicious circle of aid into positive intervention modules too (Walton, 2013).

Conclusion

There have been positive results of foreign aid particularly in health, education, sanitation and some degree of local level capacity building.

In the larger philosophical and normative level, foreign aid remains controversial and very often used for political and economic gains of donors while there is a correlation between donor countries/organizations with that of recipient countries elite which has way laid the benefits of foreign aid from the needy.

Soon after India finalized the Rafael Deal with French firm Dassault Rafale, former British Prime Minister David Cameron, lambasted India of „ingratitude“ in spite of billions of pound British foreign aid to India. The US based „Global Financial Integrity (GFI)“ and the „Centre for Applied Research at the Norwegian School of Economics“ found that in 2012, developing countries received a total of US\$1.3trillion, including all aid, investment, and income from abroad. In that same year, some US\$3.3trillion flowed out of them to developed countries. Developing countries rather sent back US\$ 2 trillion more to the rest of the world than they received. Apparently, since 1980, net outflows from developing countries add up to an eye- popping total of US\$16.3trillion – that’s how much money has been drained out of the global south over the past few decades.

Alex Dreher, Heidelberg University, empirically establishes that non-permanent members of United Nations Security Council (UNSC), soon after becoming UNSC members have negotiated more foreign assistance to their countries- a case of *quid pro quo*.

At the philosophical and normative level, the entire „Centre-Periphery“ school of thought and “Dependency Theory“ protagonists like Hans Wolfgang, Paul Baran and Andre Gunter Frank, Immanuel Wallerstein *et al* explain how the periphery (developing world) subsidizes the economic prosperity of the industrialized North- a case so amply and empirically tested to be correct. The great American Saying “No lunch is Free” is indeed true. Estonian economist Ragner Nurkse, Peruvian critique José Carlos Mariátegui *et al* have advocated indigenous growth as the best way.

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